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शिक्षण आणि समाज

वर्ष ४५, अंक ४, जुलै ते सप्टेंबर २०२२
Year 45, Issue 4, July - September 2022

इंडियन इन्स्टिट्यूट ऑफ एज्युकेशन
जे. पी. नाईक पथ, कोथरुड, पुणे- ४११ ०३८

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Development and Social Development through Education'

‘सामाजिक विकासातून शिक्षण आणि शिक्षणाद्वारा सामाजिक विकास’
ह्या धोरणास वाहिलेले त्रैमासिक

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July - September 2022

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Indian Institute of Education

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Editorial

We are very happy to publish our new issue with the various topics related to education and society. We hope that the readers will definitely like this issue.

We request to the writers, researchers, professors and students to write such a diverse range of academic and social topics. Along with this we invite the writings on the difficulties and problems in implementing the new education policy. As many of our readers want to know what the new education will be under the new education policy, we have repeated this appeal in every issue. But the satisfactory responses are expected. Writers should think about this.

In this issue, we are presenting writings by eminent scholars and research students on various topics such as counter-radicalization strategy in India, skills of Pre-service Teachers in terms of inclusive education, Total quality management in education, E-learning readiness and measurement of its dimensions, A new approach for teaching-learning process, Reflective learning practices among teachers, Future of Media education in India, Reading problems, work and life balancing of women teachers, challenges and problems of migrant youth workers, analysis of implementation of forest rights, survey of depression among women football players and study of educational awareness among fishermen community. For the first time we have included such diverse topics together in this issue.

Our quarterly is dedicated to the educational and social issues and carrying the motto of 'Education should become a social movement'. The founder of our institute, Padmabhushan educationist Prof. J. P. Naik dedicated himself throughout his life to the educational and social implementation in India. The draft of Kothari Education Commission written by him is a milestone in the progress of Indian education. He has played a significant role in universalizing and indigenizing Indian education in various forms such as distance education, open education, correspondence education, adult education, education of out-of-stream students, non-formal education etc. The work of carrying this policy is brought forward by the mouthpiece of our institute 'Education and Society'. We expect the same cooperation and love from all the authors and readers.

- Asst. Executive Editor

Education and Society
Indian Institute of Education, Pune.

WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN TEACHERS OF SIKKIM: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Punam Chhetri*

TJMS Raju**

Abstract:

Work-life balance a construct popularized in the West is fairly recent in origin. The current transformation ushered in as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic where work-from-home has become the new normal has reaffirmed the need for conducting researches in work-life balance where employees, especially women, have to juggle between work-related activities and personal life-related activities. Hence the present paper is an attempt to study the work-life balance of women teachers teaching in secondary schools of Sikkim taking few demographic variables. For this reason, a sample of 231 female teachers was selected through the Simple Random Sampling technique. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the analysis of data which was performed in SPSS version 20. Work-Life Balance Scale of Hayman (2005) was used for generating data. The study found a significant difference in the work-life balance of women teachers concerning management, on the contrary, the study revealed no significant difference in terms of the nature of the appointment, subjects handled, and experience. The findings bear implications for policy-makers in developing strategies to minimize the incidences of work-life imbalance.

Keywords: work-life balance, women, teachers

Introduction:

Ideally, work-life balance means harmonious and holistic integration of work and non-work, so that men and women are able to achieve their potential across the domains in which they play out their life roles (Baillyn, Drago, & Kochan, 2001). But more simply, the authors mention that work-life balance can be attained by meaningfully integrating work and non-work domains rather than viewing them as contrasts. Growing interests in areas of work-life balance can be mainly accounted for by the emergence of the phenomena of

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dual-earning couples, massive entry of women in the world of work as opposed to the popular belief of male as the sole breadwinner of the family, breakdown of the traditional family unit (Kreitner & Kinicki 2004) as cited in Maeran, Pitarelli & Cangiano (2013). The early studies related to work-life balance centered on the idea of conflict, the approach widely propagated by Greenhaus & Beutell (1985) which suggests that the pressures from work and family being incompatible results in a conflict-like situation. However, this notion was replaced by a more accommodating viewpoints reflected in the theory of enrichment popularised by Greenhaus and Powell (2006), which underscores that the experiences in the form of skills, behaviour, attitudes gained in either domain enrich and enhance each other. This conceptual transition has strongly influenced the research works as the researchers nowadays focus more on integrating work and non-work domains.

In the world of academia, there is a growing need for work-life balance studies since the educator has to play several roles like a researcher, advisor, and most importantly educator (Hubbard, 2016). While many still believe that the job of a teacher is relatively simple as teachers have fixed working hours which allows them sufficient time in catering to their personal needs, however the teaching-learning situation has witnessed transformation mainly in terms of pedagogy, teachers' increased workload and strives for excellence. The advent of such changes has in a way contributed to teachers' imbalanced work-life equation. In connection to this, Lahti (2017) mentions that the job of teachers has escalated as it is not confined with teaching but takes into account responsibilities like managing large class size while sustaining the quality and standard of education, planning, evaluating, coping to new adjustments brought in by technological advances and performing tasks outside their job description.

Statement of the Problem:

The problem is stated as **Work-Life Balance of Women Teachers: An empirical analysis.**

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of the study was to understand the work-life balance of women teachers of Sikkim based on management, nature of the appointment, and experience.

Hypotheses:

To address the aforementioned objectives, the following null hypotheses were formulated.

1. There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on management.
2. There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on the nature of the appointment.
3. There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on teaching experience.

Definition of the Key Terms:

Work-life balance- harmonious and holistic integration of work and non-work, so that men and women can achieve their potential across the domains in which they play out their life roles (Baillyn, Drago, & Kochan, 2001)

Research Design:

The present study attempted to investigate the status of the work-life balance of women teachers of Sikkim, therefore the study adopted a Descriptive Research design. Simple Random Sampling technique was used for generating a sample of 231 women teachers.

Research Instrument:

A standardized tool on work-life balance developed by J. Hayman (2005) consisting of fifteen items anchored around three dimensions of work-life balance-work interference with personal life (WIPL), personal life interference with work (PLIW), and work personal life enhancement (WPLE) was used for data collection.

Data Analysis:

Data was firstly tabulated in SPSS and was subjected to statistical treatment by calculating the mean SD and parametric tests were used for testing the null hypothesis.

Results of Statistical Analysis:

Keeping in tune with the objectives and null hypotheses stated earlier in the paper the results have been presented as follows:

H_{01} . There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers that based on management

The results of independent samples t test are displayed in table 1.

Table 1**Mean Comparison of Secondary School Teachers Based on Management**

Variable	Management	n	Mean	S D	t (229)	p
Overall Work-	Govt.	179	4.97	0.71		
Life Balance	Private	52	5.28	0.70	-2.82	0.00

Table 1 depicts the descriptive and inferential statistics of the work-life balance of women teachers across overall work-life balance. Women teachers teaching under govt. and private management differed significantly in terms of their overall work-life with $t(229) = -2.82, p < 0.05$. Moreover, it is also seen in the result that private school teachers with ($M = 5.28, SD = 0.70$) were ahead in their work-life balance position in contrast to government school teachers with ($M = 4.97, SD = 0.71$). Therefore, the results indicate private school teachers are having sound work-life balance than government school teachers. Consequently, H_{01} was rejected.

H_{02} . There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on the nature of the appointment

The results of statistical test conducted to test the above hypothesis are tabulated below.

Table 2**Mean Comparison of Secondary School Teachers Based on Nature of Appointment**

Variable	Appointment	n	Mean	SD	t (229)	p
Overall Work-	Regular	113	5.11	0.76		
Life Balance	Ad-hoc	118	4.97	0.68	1.52	0.13

Table 2 shows the results of independent samples t test that was conducted to test the above null hypothesis. On perusal of the table, it is clear that regular and ad-hoc female teachers did not reveal any significant difference in their overall work-life balance with $t(229) = 1.52, p > 0.05$. Therefore, based on statistical analysis, the investigator fails to reject H_{02} .

H_{03} . There is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on teaching experience

F test was computed to test the above hypothesis; results are shown below in Table 3.

Table 3

Mean, Standard Deviation and One-Way Analysis of
Variance in Work-Life Balance
Across Teaching Experience

Variables	<10 Years		10-20 Years		>20 Years		F (2, 228)
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
WLB	5.02	0.70	5.05	0.82	5.16	0.62	0.45*

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics and F- value for various work-life balance and total work-life balance across various groups of teaching experience. Results indicated no significant difference across teaching experience groups in overall work-life balance with $F(2, 228) = 0.45, p > 0.05$. Therefore, based on the above statistical results the investigator fails to reject H_0 i.e., there is no significant difference in the overall work-life balance of women teachers based on teaching experience.

Conclusion:

The problems associated with work-life balance exist for individuals from all walks of life at some point or the other. Driven by the quest for attaining quality in education, educational institutions are charged with heavy workloads which ultimately leave the teachers exhausted and who are expected to conduct themselves in a befitting manner at home. Understandably, to mitigate the work-life imbalance issues, the focus of policy-makers should be directed towards developing some work-place strategies as a way of combating the stresses caused by the imbalanced work-life situation. Strategies in the form of less stringent leave policies, creation of an appropriate atmosphere in schools where teachers can complete the professional assignments, congenial environment with the focus on building strong inter-personal ties, equal sharing of responsibilities among teachers, giving opportunities for teachers to voice out their opinions regarding various institutional matters can be effective means in improving the work-life balance of teachers especially working in government schools.

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